

WAYS TO IMPROVE MEDICINAL PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION CHANNELS

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Abstract. *In this article, distribution of goods, promotion of sales, establishment of contacts, delivery of goods in accordance with consumer demand. negotiating, organizing the movement of goods, financing and risk-taking, and distribution channels in their length, width and number of steps are considered.*

Keywords: *medicine, distribution, consumer, pharmaceutical, product, social, political, development, promotion.*

INTRODUCTION. The field of population health care is becoming an important branch of the modern economy. Not only the medical field, but also the production of pharmaceutical products and their adequate supply of enterprises and branches are gaining great importance as a separate activity. In the world, the pharmaceutical industry is the most important social sector that ensures the sustainable development of the human health care system. This is because the health care system, which is a separate direction of social policy, is primarily aimed at preventing or detecting and treating diseases in their initial stages.

Analysis of literature on the topic Scientific-theoretical aspects of improving marketing activities in the market of pharmaceutical products A. Balashov [8], Yu.N. Scientists like Kovalnogova conducted research. Scientists such as Wigglesworth, K., Zelcer, J. have described the behavior of customers of pharmaceutical companies. Also from foreign scientists to research problems in the pharmaceutical market O.A. Vasnetsova, Kareva N.I., V.I. Krikov, S.A. Lagunova, E.A. Maksimkina, V.I. Prokopishin, M.V. Ryzhkova, A.Yu. Yudanov, M. Brown, N. Evanson, JE Fincham, RA Gosselin, MC Smith, JB Thomas, AI Wertheimer contributed their work. Among the scientists of our country, Bobbojonov d.Saipova D.T., Ilyasova K.A., Yunuskhojaev A.A., A.Alimov, Sh Musaeva focused on pharmaceutical marketing.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Consists of:

The purpose of our scientific research in the market of pharmaceutical products is to suggest ways to develop marketing activities of wholesale enterprises in the drug market, including methods of sales promotion.

In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks were defined and performed in the article:

Revealing the characteristics of marketing activities in the pharmaceutical market;

Analysis of the activities of participants of the drug market in the city of Samarkand;

Analyzing marketing activities at "Biokosmik" LLC in the city of Samarkand;

Distribution channels consist of a set of intermediate links that take ownership of the goods or help sell them on the way from the producer to the consumer. As intermediate links, there can be ordinary intermediaries, wholesalers and retailers.

- The specific features of the pharmaceutical market of Samarkand region are revealed;

- The rules of marketing activities of wholesale intermediaries in the drug market have been revealed;
- The mechanism of managing wholesale and retail trade in the pharmaceutical market is disclosed;
- Methodical recommendations for product distribution and sales promotion have been developed in pharmaceutical trade.

Selling goods directly to the final consumer is carried out by means of offering goods in a retail enterprise - "merchandising", licensed trade - "franchising" and establishing direct contact with the consumer - "direct marketing". The use of intermediaries is that they can offer the goods in the most appropriate form, relying on their experience and high quality of work, thereby bringing more profit to the manufacturer. At the same time, an increase in the number of intermediaries can lead to an increase in the price of goods, a slowdown in circulation and, in general, an increase in the cost of the entire process of goods movement.

The fact is that at "BIOCOSMIC" LLC they produce medicinal products in a narrow range that allows you to make the right choice based on your needs. The work of changing the assortment is entrusted to intermediaries, through which they play a positive role in many ways in exploring partnership relations and concluding deals with manufacturers on this basis. Among them are informational functions, sales promotion, communication, and bringing goods in line with consumer demand. negotiating, organizing the movement of goods, financing and taking risks deserve the most attention. Distribution channels are characterized by their length, width and number of steps. Intermediate links of commodity movement are shown as steps. In turn, the sum of intermediate joints forms the length of the distribution channel. In this case, the producer of the goods is the initial link of the channel, and the consumers are the final link of the channel.

A single-step channel includes a small wholesale link in addition to the retailer and wholesaler. In the practice of trade, channels with a larger number of intermediate links can also be encountered, but they are of less importance in the organization of the movement of goods.

Today, the company "BIOCOSMIC" LLC is organized in a four-step method. A single-step channel is usually called a proper marketing channel, because it consists of the beginning and the end links, that is, there are no intermediate links. Direct sales tend to grow, especially in developed economies. This channel is almost never used in the sale of pharmaceutical products.

A two-step channel usually has one intermediate link, which is the retailer. This type is common among manufacturers of food, agricultural products, construction materials, etc. These types of channels are almost non-existent in "BIOCOSMIC" LLC.

The three-step channel is completed by the wholesaler as well as the retailer. This channel is used by manufacturers of some types of additional sophisticated household appliances, pharmaceuticals, and food products. "BIOCOSMIC" LLC can be considered a representative of such a channel, but many drugs cause the channel to become more complicated.

In addition to the retailer and wholesaler, the four-step channel also includes a small wholesale link. In trade practice, channels with a larger number of intermediate links can also be found, but they do not play a prominent role in the organization of goods movement. Each distribution channel has its own organizational structure and in this sense the channel participant interacts with other links. But the company "BIOCOSMIC" LLC itself, especially its well-being, in many ways is a reflection of the competent implementation of sales and customer service

processes at points. The productivity of the participant taken separately is determined by two factors:

- first, with the performance level of the entire distribution channel;
- secondly, with the ability of this channel to compete with other wine and spirits producing channels.

The distribution channel selection process relies on optimizing efforts across space and time to first identify specific partners that can positively impact the product's direct-to-consumer movement.

In general, the number of intermediaries in the "producer-consumer" chain and their functions vary from product to product, region to region, and country to country. Most participants of the channel only buy and resell the goods, while others try to pay more attention to marketing activities. The experience of European countries testifies to certain trends in the development and improvement of the distribution channel in general, including its individual elements. On the surface, their meaning is as follows:

- the number of intermediate links in the distribution channels is decreasing due to the use of transport systems for the delivery of goods and the improvement of information transmission, as well as due to the decrease in the role of wholesale trade, instead of the strengthening of the position of manufacturers, who in many cases prove the possibility of performing the functions of wholesalers (also, the initiators of these directions are retailers division is also possible);

- increased control over the formation of price policy in distribution channels, large companies trying to create their own distribution systems against the aggressive policy of retail sales;

- significant changes are taking place in the use of free and working time by the population, which in turn will lead to the use of rational and efficient methods of distribution channel sales technology, self-service, microprocessors (especially their programming capabilities), saving consumers' free time and at the same time and leading to a re-evaluation of aspects such as the development of supermarkets and shop clubs that enable service delivery.

Product distribution improvement includes direct and accurate delivery of information about the product to consumers, effective use of mass media, television, and radio in this regard.

In addition, the competitiveness of the manufactured product should be high.

In "BIOCOSMIC" LLC, along with improving the quality and competitiveness of products produced in other enterprises, it is important that the buyer has the ability to pay for the sale of goods. Therefore, the demand is also called "solvent demand".

Sales promotion is commercial and marketing activities aimed at increasing sales over a period of time, as well as the work of pharmaceutical employees in a pharmacy organization:

- stimulation of consumer demand;
- improving the quality of service;
- speeding up the process of goods circulation and sale of goods;
- positioning of the product/manufacturer's brand.

There are two activity blocks in the activity complex:

- 1) activity aimed at the final consumer of drugs and pharmacy products. They should encourage a trial or repeat purchase, as well as an increase in the frequency of consumption of pharmacy products. The ultimate goal of these activities is to increase consumer engagement;

2) pharmacy organizations as a member of the distribution network - measures aimed at promoting the distribution network. They are aimed at developing distribution, accelerating turnover and increasing sales.

Marketing activity aimed at the pharmacy organization is a set of measures aimed at promoting its sales, accelerating the turnover of goods and increasing the volume of sales. These measures include:

- affiliate loyalty programs or loyalty programs based on reciprocal marketing. The customer creates a bonus card with offers from program partners. For each purchase, he receives points on the card, which can be used as a discount for purchases or gifts from partners.

- motivation of employees of pharmaceutical organizations. Motivation is the process of external influence on an employee to successfully complete a task or to perform an effective job in general. There is internal and external stimulation. External incentives for certain volumes of drug sales are provided by distributors and/or manufacturers. Internal incentives depend on the performance of the pharmacy organization.

When buying goods, people intend to satisfy certain needs. Therefore, it is a responsible period for the company to enter the market, information about the quality indicators of the goods is not provided. The prospective consumer must receive the following information:

- availability of goods and place of sale;
- which needs are aimed at satisfaction;
- basic indicators of consumer value;
- Guarantees to protect customers in the event of dissatisfaction.

Methods of communicating information to prospective buyers:

- Advertisements (radio, television, written).
- Conducting exhibitions.
- Meetings through conventions and films.

Addressing uninformed buyers will stimulate their demand and encourage them to buy the product.

So, one of the main reasons for the formation of demand is to be able to interest customers in the product by providing them with correct and accurate information about the product, and attracting the consumer with the appearance and packaging of the product. Sales promotion refers to consumers who have a certain level of information about the product. Therefore, the task of the incentive policy is to make them eager to buy the company's goods in the future and to encourage them to keep in touch.

Demand generation activities are usually aimed at consumers and sellers. Incentives for consumers are intended to provide them with significant commercial benefits:

- a privilege given to the volume of purchase of goods and to stay in constant contact;
- sale of goods for various forms of debt;
- distribution of samples free of charge with a view to purchasing goods in large quantities;
- free supply of goods for temporary use;
- acceptance of used goods under certain conditions;
- showing new goods to prospective buyers;
- organization of trips to enterprises producing goods;
- conducting press conferences dedicated to the introduction of new products to the market;

- announcements on the radio, television and press about a sharp reduction in the price of goods.

The promotion policy for the products depends on the type of customers who buy them. It is intended to encourage intermediaries, to increase their activity and initiative, and to expand the circle of consumers. The policy of demand formation and sales promotion must correspond to the life stages of the product in the market and give appropriate content to each of them.

Personal selling / direct marketing

At the behest of the manufacturer or in accordance with the database compiled by him, or by receiving feedback from a specific consumer, represents the effect on a specific audience. The essence of the method is to personalize the advertising message. It is customary to distinguish five traditional forms of direct marketing: direct mail marketing, catalog marketing, telemarketing (marketing by telephone, telecommunications technologies and database management systems for marketing purposes), television marketing (advertisement on television, use of special commercial channels developed). transmission of commercial and advertising information, after reading which the consumer can order goods at competitive prices without leaving home), e-commerce.

Public relations - coordinating efforts to create a positive image of a particular product in the minds of consumers. The purpose of promotion is to attract the attention of potential consumers without advertising costs.

Main means of promotion:

- **speeches: participation of representatives of pharmaceutical manufacturers and pharmaceutical organizations at the opening of various events, etc.;**
- **events: organization of press conferences, seminars and anniversaries, participation in exhibitions, contests and contests, etc.;**
- **news: providing the mass media with positive news about the pharmaceutical organization and its employees (press releases);**
- **publications: annual reports, newsletters, brochures, magazine or newspaper articles and other printed materials used as a means of influencing target markets;**
- **sponsorship: allocation of time, financial and material resources to support the organization of charitable, sports and other socially significant events;**
- **means of identification: use of the emblem (logo) of the pharmaceutical organization, writing paper with watermarks and other markings, corporate-style packaging materials, business cards, creation of websites, development and implementation of uniform style and design of buildings.**

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The conducted theoretical and practical research allowed us to come to the following conclusions.

As a result of the conducted research, we developed a number of recommendations for the distribution and promotion of sales at "BIOCOSMIC" LLC, and their content is as follows:

1. In order to be superior to competitors, it is desirable to introduce differentiation of orders for medicines, that is, separation by classifications. In particular, grouping drug products by order size and repeat order is one way to meet customer needs.

2. Including forecasting and monitoring the demand for medicinal products We offer as one of the ways to improve sales at "BIOCOSMIC" LLC.

3. It is necessary to further improve the system of incentives for buyers. For this, it is recommended to study advanced foreign and local experience. Another goal of "BIOCOSMIC" LLC is to train and improve the skills of personnel in marketing methods.

4. Since e-commerce has a very small contribution to the turnover of "BIOCOSMIC" LLC today, one of our recommendations is the development of network marketing and e-commerce.

5. Due to the fact that "BIOCOSMIC" LLC is a young, newly formed enterprise, it is necessary to pay more attention to the development of marketing strategy.

The implementation of these recommendations will serve to improve the distribution system of medicines at "BIOCOSMIC" LLC.

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